

International Journal of Advances in Engineering & Scientific Research (IJAESR)

ISSN: 2349 -3607 (Online) , ISSN: 2349 -4824 (Print)

Download Full paper from :

<http://www.arseam.com/content/volume-1-issue-8-dec-2014>

Submit paper Email: editor@arseam.com

Contact us: info@arseam.com

For detail, visit: <http://www.arseam.com/>

PHARMACOGENOMICS: A STEP AHEAD IN MODERN DAY DRUG DISCOVERY

Meetal Sinha², M Kalim A Khan^{1,2}, M Haris Siddiqui^{1,2}, Usman Sayeed², Gulshan Wadhwa³ and Salman Akhtar^{1,2*}

1. Advanced Centre for Bioengineering and Bioinformatics (ACBB), Integral Research Centre (IRC), Integral University, Lucknow, India -226026
2. Department of Bioengineering, Faculty of Engineering, Integral University, Lucknow, India – 226026
3. Department of Biotechnology, Ministry of Science and Technology, CGO complex, Government of India, India - 110003

Abstract

There has been a steady advancement in life science research and development. One of the major emerging trends in bioengineering is the study of pharmacogenomics. Pharmacogenomics is a science of using genetic information from an individual or population to determine drug efficacy and drug safety as well as to identify responder and non responder to a drug. Though it has already been recognized that genetic differences existing between individuals, contribute as to why different people responds to the same drugs differently. A lot of research has been performed for the complete analysis of the pharmacogenomics progress. This review is just a small step to explain the history, its current status, its future predictions and potential challenges that need to be overcome to get the maximum benefit of the study. A number of drugs are also assembled in this paper which possesses higher potential to be personalized.

Keywords: Pharmacogenomics, Pharmacogenetics, Drug Efficacy, Drug Safety

Introduction

Individual response for drugs varies in different ways. Children, under the age of 6, should not take cough and cold medicines as it poses long term harm to body, though not in adults. For most of the people, Brompheniramine is used to relieve symptoms of allergy, and hay fever but pregnant women are strictly prohibited to use this medication. Penicillin is tolerated by most of the people but; about one out of 10,000 patients who use it could go into life-threatening anaphylactic shock. [1] The field of pharmacogenomics was created several years ago as physicians were aware of the subtle differences between patients in their responses to medications.

In 1957, Arno Motulsky [2] wrote about how 'drug reactions may be considered pertinent models for demonstrating the interaction of heredity and environment in the pathogenesis of disease'. In 1959, the German Pharmacologist Friedrich Vogel coined the term pharmacogenetics, a term used to denote the science about how hereditary factors affect the response to drugs [3]. More recently in 1997, Marshall coined the term 'pharmacogenomics' [4]. Pharmacogenomics differed from pharmacogenetics in about how all the human genes, their products and their variations are identified systematically, which may be used both to design new drugs and to predict the right treatment for each individual. Both terms are used in similar manner; however, pharmacogenomics signifies that we have the ability to evaluate the whole genome through our current knowledge and advanced technology rather than just working on a single gene [5].

Pharmacogenomics: From the days of past

In early 510 BC, Pythagoras [6] described the first example of pharmacogenetics trait known as favism. Certain Mediterranean populations developed red blood cell haemolysis by eating uncooked fava beans [6] which were later recognized as a deficiency of glucose-6-phosphate dehydrogenase (G6PD).

The period between 1950 and 1980 saw various researches being conducted on the variation in drug metabolizing enzyme genes observing the phenotypic changes [7], such as the muscle relaxant suxamethonium chloride, and drugs metabolized by *N*-acetyltransferase. The less efficient variant of the butyrylcholinesterase enzyme that metabolizes suxamethonium chloride caused slower recovery from surgical paralysis. *N*-acetyltransferase catalyzes the *N*-acetylation and *O*-acetylation of arylamine carcinogens and heterocyclic amines. Slow acetylators phenotype of *N*-acetyltransferase were often seen experiences toxicity from drugs such as isoniazid, sulfonamides, procainamide, and hydralazine, whereas the fast acetylator phenotype did not respond to isoniazid and hydralazine in the management of tuberculosis and hypertension, respectively.

With the advancement in the molecular biological techniques, the phenotypic driven assessments of the genes were later found to be related to the nucleotide substitutions. The best example is debrisoquine hydroxylase or CYP2D6 polymorphism [8]. The activity of the phase I cytochrome P450 enzyme was defined by the hydroxylation of debrisoquine, later named as CYP2D6 [9]. Hence for drugs that were metabolized by CYP2D6, certain individuals were found to be ultra-rapid metabolizers [10] while others were poor metabolizers. Efficacy of the drug was reduced if the drug is rapidly metabolized [11] and on the counterpart if the drug metabolism is too slow, it is certain to result in toxicity [12]. An association between the normal or rapid metabolism of CYP2D6 phenotype suggested an increased risk of lung and bladder cancer [13].

This era was succeeded by the age of PCR-based techniques which enabled molecular assessment of many genes, such as *CYP2D6*, *TPMT*, *CYP2C9* and *UGT1A1*, which were recommended to help to make treatment decisions, but the use of genotyping was still in its growing phase as most of the studies were still largely limited to single genes .

During the last 10 years, a number of polymorphic genes have also been discovered and shown to alter drug responses and have profound impact on drug disposition, drug efficacy, and drug safety. Mostly these genes encode drug transporters and drug targets [11]. Best evidence for polymorphism in drug transporters are *ABCB1* gene encoding the P-glycoprotein and ABC transporter (*ABCG2*) encoding breast cancer resistance protein. Polymorphisms in genes encoding drug targets directly produce profound effects on drug response like the angiotensin I-converting enzyme (*ACE*) encoded by the *ACE* gene . An insertion and deletion polymorphism of *ACE* has shown to affect *ACE* inhibition therapy in a number of diseases [14].

The assessment of the whole genome was possible only after the completion of the Human Genome Project in 2003 whereby the true advent of pharmacogenomics era was witnessed [15]. The association of sequence variations and heritable clinical phenotypes of drug responses was majorly possible due to rapid sequencing and genotyping of SNPs.

510 BC	Pythagoras recognised the dangers of ingesting fava beans, later characterised to be because of deficiency of G6PD[16]
1866	Mendel Established of the rules of heredity [17]
1906	Garrod -Publication of 'Inborn Errors of Metabolism'
1932	Snyder Characterized the 'phenylthiourea nontaster' as an autosomal recessive trait [18]
1956	Alving et al. Discover glucose-6-phosphate dehydrogenase deficiency [19]
1957	Motulsky Further refined the concept that inherited defects of metabolism could explain individual differences in drug response[3]
1960	Kalow and Genest Characterized of serum cholinesterase deficiency [20] Vogel Coined the term pharmacogenetics [2] Price Evans Characterized acetylator polymorphism [21]
1962	Kalow- Publication of 'Pharmacogenetics – Heredity and the Response to Drugs' [22]
1977/79	Mahgoub et al. and Eichelbaum et al. Discover of the polymorphism in debrisoquine hydroxylase [23,24]
1985	PCR allows genetic sequences to be amplified exponentially
1987	First nomenclature of the <i>P450</i> -supergene family.
1988	Gonzalez et al. Characterized of the genetic defect in debrisoquine hydroxylase, later termed CYP2D6[9]
1988-90	Gonzalez and Meyer collaborated to clone <i>CYP2D6</i> and characterize the genetic defect of the debrisoquine/sparteine polymorphism[25,26]
1990	
1991	Heim and Meyer published the first allele-specific pharmacogenetic gene test for <i>CYP2D6</i> [27]
1993	The first issue of the journal <i>Pharmacogenetics</i> is published.
1994	Johansson, Ingelman-Sundberg and Bertilsson discover that stable gene amplifications of <i>CYP2D6</i> cause the ultrarapid-metabolizer phenotype[28,29,30]
1995	Cloning and characterization of <i>CYP2C19</i> , which causes the mephenytoin polymorphism, by Goldstein <i>et al.</i> [31].
1997	A committee (Vatsis <i>et al.</i>) offers a nomenclature for <i>NAT</i> alleles[6]. Krynetzki <i>et al.</i> publish the first mutations of the <i>TPMT</i> gene, from which a DNA test is derived [32].

1999	The term pharmacogenomics first appears in the literature.
1988-2000	A nomenclature website for the human cytochrome P450 (CYP) allele is established by an international committee. A public/private collaboration, the 'SNP Consortium', provides public information on genomic diversity.
2000	Various Identification of specific polymorphisms in various phase I and phase II drug metabolising enzymes, and latterly in drug transporters
2001	The first comprehensive pharmacogenetic knowledge base, the 'PharmGKB' web site, is constructed on the basis of the National Institutes of Health Pharmacogenetics Research Network.
2001-03	A draft of the human genome sequence is published.
2003	Public-private partnership Completion of the initial draft and complete sequence of the human genome [33,34]
2004	The International HapMap Project -Completion of map of human genome sequence variation [35] The Federal Drug Administration issues draft guidelines for submission of pharmacogenetic data with new drug applications.
2006	Characterization of >1.8 million SNPs by the SNP Consortium.
2007	Reddon et al. Global map of copy number variation [36]
2011	Wellcome Trust Case-Control Consortium Genome-wide association in 14,000 cases in seven diseases [37] 1000 genomes project A map of human genome variation based on population-scale genome sequencing[38]

Courtesy: Meyer Urs A (Nature Reviews volume 5. 669 -675)& Pirmohamed ,M (Drug Discovery Today, Volume 16,Numbers 19/20.)

Current status of pharmacogenomics studies:

It is not necessary that all the drugs work for all patients. A prescribed drug works in some patients but not in others. Traditionally drug development and clinical therapies have involved approaches such as 'trial and error ', 'one drug fits all 'and 'one dose fits all' which has drastically contributed to 25-50% of drug toxicity and treatment failure[39]. Similarly an adverse drug reaction (ADRs) is seen in some patients but not all. In order to reduce adverse drug reactions, drugs are thoroughly monitored for safety and efficacy. Though all the approved drugs are brought in the market only after strict evaluations and according to regulatory guidelines of FDA for safety and efficacy of a drug, still it is found to be unsafe for many individuals due to genetic and environmental factors. Variations in drug responses can be discussed at following levels.

1. Acquired/Environmental/Non genetic sources of variability:

i) Age, sex, body mass (variations of individuals), ii) Intake of tobacco iii) Smoking habit iv) use of alcoholic drinks, v)Disease status vi) Vitamin K proportion vii) Medications/ nutritional supplements regularly used[40,41]

2. Genetic sources of variability:

The genetic makeup of every individual is unique, variability occurs in the expression of gene products such as drug metabolizing enzymes, their downstream signal transporters and targets. As for example people with *CYP2C9**2 and *3 SNPs/alleles have reduced warfarin metabolism and therefore require lower warfarin doses [39,40].

A person's response to a drug is based on the haplotypes or combinations of variants they inherit from their parents. "Metabolizer type" refers to how well a person can break down the drug in the body. Based on patients' metabolizer type, effective dosage can be determined whether they need a higher dose or lower dose of medication than what is normally prescribed [42] paving the way for personalized medicine which refers to tailoring of medical treatment with respect to the individual characteristic requirements.

The genetic variations are often variations in alleles of genes involved in drug metabolism. Some polymorphisms speed up the metabolism, leading to under treatment; others inhibit the drug breakdown, leading to the risk of overdoses. The example below refers to the possible metabolizer types for the *CYP2C19* gene. This gene encodes for an enzyme which is used to break down clopidogrel. Different haplotypes on the *CYP2C19* gene can be used to predict how a person may react to clopidogrel [42].

Reduced CYP2C19 activity	Typical CYP2C19 activity	Increased CYP2C19 activity
Poor metabolizer	Extensive metabolizer	Ultra-rapid metabolizer
Does not receive maximum benefit from the drug.	Expected to get benefit from standard dose.	Expected to process medication/treatment more quickly.

Courtesy: <http://cpmc1.coriell.org/personalized-medicine>

Some examples of drug that have great potential for personalization have been summarized below.

Warfarin

Warfarin is an anticoagulant drug with a narrow therapeutic index and a wide range of interindividual variability in dose requirement. Warfarin appears within the top three prescribed drugs for causing adverse drug reaction in most epidemiological studies [1, 43]. Since it is difficult to predict an accurate dose for an individual, patients have a 2-3 times increased risk of thromboembolism or in simpler words bleeding associated with under dosing or over dosing of medication when they start the drug. Cytochrome P450 2C9 (*CYP2C9*) Variants that alter warfarin dose are *CYP2C9**2 and *CYP2C9**3. Two common vitamin K epoxide reductase (*VKOR*) haplotypes are Haplotype A (variant 1&2) and Haplotype B (variant 7, 8 & 9). Taken together, environmental and genetic factors can account for approximately 50% of the variation in daily dose requirements for warfarin. Although the single nucleotide polymorphisms in *CYP2C9* and *VKOR* plays a vital role in

variability in warfarin dose requirement, currently available evidence based on a few small studies relating to the use of pharmacogenetics-guided dosing in the initiation of warfarin therapy has not shown improved outcomes in either safety or efficacy of therapy [43,44,45].

Midazolam

Midazolam is a benzodiazepine central nervous system depressant. Midazolam is primarily metabolized in the liver and gut by human cytochrome P450 3A4 (CYP3A4) to its pharmacologic active metabolite, α -hydroxymidazolam. There is no evidence that polymorphisms (CYP3A3, CYP3A4, CYP3A5) cause any effect in drug action. However, coadministration of midazolam with fentanyl or nitrendipine can cause prolongation in the action of drugs as both fentanyl and nitrendipine are metabolized by cytochrome P450 3A enzymes. Fentanyl metabolism gets inhibited by midazolam's competing metabolism at the liver enzyme CYP3A4 whereas Nitrendipine metabolism has shown to inhibit human liver hydroxylation of midazolam. These information may prove beneficial to drug interactions building in combined therapy [46,47].

Succinylcholine

Succinylcholine is a depolarizing muscle relaxant used for relaxing muscles during surgery. Succinylcholine is the only available neuromuscular blocker with a rapid onset of stimulation in just 60 seconds and recovery of muscle strength in 9 to 13 minutes which is due to the rapid hydrolysis of Butyrylcholinesterase. The genetic variants of Butyrylcholinesterase can significantly prolong the succinylcholin-induced neuromuscular blockade. People who are homozygous for this polymorphism have prolongation of drug from 4-8 hours than normal. Heterozygotes lengthen the blockade response by 50%-100%. [48,49,50]

Carbamazepine

Carbamazepine is one of the most widely used anti epileptic drug as it has a good record at reducing frequency of epileptic seizures though as many as 40% of patients experience pharmacoresistance. Sometimes serious and fatal dermatologic reactions, including toxic epidermal necrolysis (TEN), drug reaction with eosinophilia and systemic symptoms (DRESS) and Stevens-Johnson syndrome (SJS), have been reported with the treatment. The HLA alleles (HLA-B*1502 and HLA-A*3101) are the most important pharmacogenomic variants for carbamazepine. Prior to treatment, testing for HLA-B*1502 is recommended in patients [51-55].

IL28B and response to interferon-a in hepatitis C

Three percent of world's population is infected by Hepatitis C virus. A combination of PEGylated interferon-alpha and ribavirin is used in the treatment of chronic Hepatitis C [56]. Effects of the IL28B polymorphisms may differ in HIV-infected patients as it is seen that in acute hepatitis C has IL28B gene associated with serum levels of hepatitis C virus RNA, g-GT, and CD4 cell count while HIV-infected patients with chronic hepatitis C, the IL28B genotype was not significantly associated with treatment response. [57,58,59]

Thiopurines

The structural analogues of purines are 6-mercaptopurine (6-MP), 6-thioguanine (6-TG) and azathioprine (AZA). Thiopurine drugs are used for the treatment of various diseases like 6-MP and 6-TG are used in the treatment of acute leukemia and lymphoma [60] and AZA is used in the treatment of rheumatoid arthritis and autoimmune hemolytic anemia. Thiopurine methyltransferase (TPMT) metabolizes the S-methylation of thiopurine drugs [61]. The mutations within the TPMT gene cause interindividual differences in

enzyme activity [60]. Patients with reduced TPMT enzyme activity develop toxic effects after the application of standard doses of these drugs while patients with high enzyme activity do not respond to standard doses of drugs. Genotyping before the initiation of treatment with these drugs is recommended [39].

Phenytoin

Phenytoin is a widely used anti-epileptic drug. It has narrow therapeutic index and wide inter-individual range of doses is required. It is metabolized mainly by CYP2C9 and by CYP2C19 to its metabolite 5-(para-hydroxyphenyl)-5-phenylhydantoin (p-HPPH). Since both these genes shows polymorphism, the effect of overall metabolism is reduced. Often it is not preferred as a first-choice medication for young children because it may have side effects when used for a long time [62]. Phenytoin is listed in Pregnancy Category D by the Food and Drug Administration (FDA). This means that there is a risk to the baby, but at times the benefits may outweigh the risk for some women[63].

Codeine

Codeine is an opiate narcotic that is used to treat moderate pain and cough. Codeine generally causes drowsiness or dizziness, and confusion. Codeine is metabolized to morphine by the cytochrome P450 enzyme CYP2D6 which shows significant genetic variation in activity [64]. Up to 10% of the white population are poor metabolizers of codeine and get no analgesic effect from this drug. This suggested that there are possibilities of low drug absorption in this population. There is also a small population of individuals, most commonly seen in persons of East African descent, who are ultra-rapid metabolizers that is these individuals convert the majority of codeine into morphine [65,66].

Potential benefits of pharmacogenomics:

Though the field of pharmacogenomics is under the preliminary developmental stages, but it certainly forecast a major revolution in the field of drug design and efficacy.

More powerful medicines and vaccines: Medicines will be developed as per the need of individual health problems in order to maximize the therapeutic effects. Vaccines made of genetic material could activate the immune system in a more efficient way to have all the benefits of existing vaccines but with reduced risks of infections. [67,68]

More accurate dosages and safer drugs: Physicians will prescribe drugs on the basis of genetic requirements instead for the used trial method which imposes higher risk of adverse effect. Accurate dosages would be given to the patient instead of dosage decided for all which will reduce the risk of over dosage and under dosage.

Advanced screening for disease: Advance knowledge of a disease will be beneficial for the early treatment and thus the patients can improve the lifestyle. May the detection is at an early age when the cure is possible and maximum efforts can be made to cure it.

Improvements in the drug discovery and approval process: Development of new drugs to overcome adverse drug reaction and optimization of drug metabolism and pharmacokinetics are two ways pharmacogenomics can be used to improve drug discovery. The drug approval process will also be enhanced as clinical trials would be more targets oriented and performed on participants capable of responding to a drug thus saving the cost and risk of trials.

Decrease in the overall cost of health care: A net decrease in the cost of health care can be achieved as there would be decreases in the number of ADRs, failed drug trials, the duration of the treatment, and drug approval process with increase in the range of possible drug targets [69].

Limitations to pharmacogenomics:

The following limitations will have to be overcome before many benefits of pharmacogenomics can be realized.

Education Barriers: Lack of education and training in the field of pharmacogenetics is one of the most challenging factors. At present, any healthcare professional does not have enough knowledge of what is pharmacogenetics data, how the patient's data should be analyzed and what action has to be taken thereafter. Presently, physicians' decision is based on drug – prescription instead of patients' genetic requirements or pharmacogenetics test. [70,71].

Financial Barriers: Lower the cost, better the technology. Cost will always be a potent barrier in developing newer technologies. At present, pharmaceutical companies spend around USD 1.3 billion to bring a drug to market, these generated drugs are supposed to fit all. After incorporating pharmacogenomics policies, drugs will either have to be generated for each individual separately or these companies will divide the patients in two categories – one that can use the drug and others who cannot which indeed will reduce their market. Now the question arises why these companies will invest millions of dollars to generate individual drugs or drugs that benefit only a tiny population. Even if they agree to do so they could ask for any desired price of the drug and the patients under pressure of being cured would be forced to pay high amounts.[72]

Evidence Barriers: The strength of the evidence that is required to approve personalized drugs and regulatory guidelines for the pharmacogenetics test are few apparent questions where reaction of FDA remains uncertain.

Limitation in drug alternatives: There are only very few drugs which are finally approved and accepted for a treatment that means if a patient is unable to get benefit or cured by the approved drugs due to his genetic variations, he would be left with no alternative options for his treatment. [73]

Complexity of finding gene variations that affect drug response: The Human Genome Project has successfully determined that the human genome is 3 billion base pairs long where Single nucleotide polymorphisms (SNPs) occur every 100 to 300 bases. Detection of SNPs and acknowledging their role in disease plays a vital role in many diseases that have a strong genetic component as a causative agent. Complexity of finding which genes are involved in a particular disease and is affecting a drug response is one of the major barriers in implementation of pharmacogenomics.

Ethical Issues: The prominent ethical issues that may arise are [74,75,76] –
Privacy- The most critical issue is privacy of the individuals who undergo pharmacogenetics tests. Following questions should be properly answered by the healthcare professionals before a test is performed-

- (a) What all tests may be performed?
- (b) How the genetic material will be handled?
- (c) How and by whom the data will be utilized?
- (d) Where the genetic material will be stored?
- (e) How secure the DNA banks are?
- (f) How the data will be maintained for future use?

Now a big question arises whether a participant will still feel secure as his genetic data is in safe hands and will not be misused. What has to be done if he denies performing the test?

Consent –Informed consent from the participants should also be taken before hand for future use. Participants’ permission on whether his family should be informed about the test and its results is still uncertain.

Equality-The cost of these pharmacogenomics techniques should be equal to all irrespective of nations, or status.

Mental trauma- If a participant is informed in his teenage that once you are in late forties, *xyz* chronic disease will affect you as per genetic test conducted whose cure is unavailable. He will spend rest twenty of his life in a mental trauma even before he is actually affected by the disease. What has to be done in this case?

Social Issues: A lot of information about a community can be deduced from the family tree which could be easily constructed just by knowing the genotype of one person. Pharmaceutical companies will have to take consent from the participant of the test but what about the whole community whose information can be traced out from the test individual [77]. Furthermore development of personalized drug destined for specific individuals owing to their unique genotype may create issues related to distributive justice and societal divisions in the community [78,79,80].

Conclusions

Pharmacogenomics is a revolution in the field of modern science. It has the potential for both drug safety and drug efficacy. Although there are many benefits of pharmacogenomics, there are also significant barriers to be overcome, for successful implementation of “Right drug in right dose for right person” instead of present “one drug fits all” conditions.

References

- 1) Henry T. Greely, JD. Pharmacogenomics: promise, prospects, and potential problems. *Medical Ethics* 2002: 9(1): 1-2
- 2) Motulsky, A.G. Drug reactions enzymes, and biochemical genetics. *J. Am.Med. Assoc.* 1957: 165: 835–837
- 3) Vogel, F. Moderne probleme der Humangenetik. *Ergeb. Inn. Med.Kinderheilkd.* 1959:12 : 52–125
- 4) Marshall, A. Genset-Abbott deal heralds pharmacogenomics era. *Nat.Biotechnol.*1997 :15: 829–830
- 5) Pirmohamed, M. Pharmacogenetics and pharmacogenomics. *Br. J. Clin.Pharmacol.* 2001:52: 345–347
- 6) Nebert, D.W. et al. From human genetics and genomics to pharmacogenetics and pharmacogenomics: past lessons, future directions. *Drug Metab. Rev.* 2008: 40: 187–224
- 7) Luzzatto, L. The rise and fall of the antimalarial Lapdap: a lesson in pharmacogenetics. *Lancet* 2010: 376:739–741
- 8) Gonzalez, F.J. et al. Characterization of the common genetic-defect in humans deficient in debrisoquine metabolism. *Nature* .1988: 331:442–446
- 9) Pirmohamed ,M. Pharmacogenetics: past, present, future. *Drug Discovery Today*, 2011 : 16: 19-20.

- 10) Aklillu, E. et al. Frequent distribution of ultrarapid metabolizers of debrisoquine in an ethiopian population carrying duplicated and multiduplicated functional CYP2D6 alleles. *J. Pharmacol. Exp. Ther.* 1996; 278: 441–446
- 11) Hong-Guang Xie & Felix W Frueh Pharmacogenomics step towards personalized medicines future *Medicine* .2005: 325-337
- 12) Teh LK, Bertilsson L. Pharmacogenomics of CYP2D6: molecular genetics, interethnic differences and clinical importance". *Drug Metab. Pharmacokinet.* 2012;27(1): 55–67. doi:10.2133/dmpk.DMPK-11-RV-121. PMID 22185816
- 13) Febbo PG, Kantoff PW, Giovannucci E, Brown M, Chang G, Hennekens CH, Stampfer M. Debrisoquine hydroxylase (CYP2D6) and prostate cancer. *Cancer Epidemiol Biomarkers Prev.*1998;7(12):1075-8.
- 14) Qiang Ma and Anthony Y. H. Lu. Pharmacogenetics, Pharmacogenomics, and Individualized Medicine. *Pharmacol Rev.* 2011: 63:437–459.
- 15) Meyer, U.A. Pharmacogenetics – five decades of therapeutic lessons from genetic diversity. *Nat. Rev. Genet.* 2004: 5: 669–676
- 16) Nebert, D W. Pharmacogenetics and Pharmacogenomics: why is this relevant to the clinical geneticist? *Clin Genet.*1999;56:247-258
- 17) Mendel, G. (1866) Versuche u̇ber Pflanzenhybriden. Verhandlungen des naturforschenden Vereines in Bru̇nn, Bd. IV fu̇r das Jahr 1865. Abhandlungen 3–47
- 18) Snyder, L.H. Studies in human inheritance IX. The inheritance of human deficiency in man. *Ohio J. Sci.* 1932;32: 436–468
- 19) Alving, A.S. et al. Enzymatic deficiency in primaquine-sensitive erythrocytes. *Science* 1956: 124: 484–485
- 20) Kalow, W. and Genest, K. A method for the detection of atypical forms of human serum cholinesterase. Determination of dibucaine numbers. *Can. J. Biochem. Physiol.* 1957: 35: 39–346
- 21) Price-Evans, D.A. et al. Genetic control of isoniazid metabolism in man. *Br. Med. J.* 1960;2: 485–491
- 22) Kalow, W. Pharmacogenetics – Heredity and Responses to Drugs. W. B Saunders Company. 1962
- 23) Mahgoub, A. et al. Polymorphic hydroxylation of debrisoquine in man. *Lancet.*1977;2: 584–586
- 24) Eichelbaum, M. et al. Defective N-oxidation of sparteine in man, a new pharmacogenetic defect. *Eur. J. Clin. Pharmacol.* 1979;16: 183–187
- 25) Skoda, R. C., Gonzalez, F. J., Demierre, A. & Meyer, U.A. Two mutant alleles of the human cytochrome P-450db1 gene (*P450C2D1*) associated with genetically deficient metabolism of debrisoquine and other drugs. *Proc. Natl Acad. Sci. USA*,1988: 85: 5240–5243.
- 26) Distlerath, L. M. *et al.* Purification and characterization of the human liver cytochromes P-450 involved in debrisoquine 4-hydroxylation and phenacetin O-deethylation, two

prototypes for genetic polymorphism in oxidative drug metabolism. *J. Biol. Chem.* 1985;260: 9057–9067

27) Heim, M. & Meyer, U. A. Genotyping of poor metabolisers of debrisoquine by allele-specific PCR amplification. *Lancet* 1990;336: 529–532.

28) Johansson, I. *et al.* Inherited amplification of an active gene in the cytochrome P450 *CYP2D* locus as a cause of ultrarapid metabolism of debrisoquine. *Proc. Natl Acad. Sci. USA* 1993; 90: 11825–11829.

29) Bertilsson, L., Aberg-Wistedt, A. & Gustaffson, L. L. Extremely rapid hydroxylation of debrisoquine; a case report with implication for treatment with nortriptyline and other tricyclic antidepressants. *Ther. Drug. Monit.* 1985;7:478–480.

30) Bertilsson, L. *et al.* Molecular basis for rational megaprescribing in ultrarapid hydroxylators of debrisoquine. *Lancet* 1993;341: 63.

31) de Morais, S. M. F. *et al.* Identification of a new genetic defect responsible for the polymorphism of *S*-mephenytoin metabolism in Japanese. *Mol. Pharmacol.* 1994;46:594–598.

32) Weinshilboum, R. Inheritance and drug response. *N. Engl. J. Med.* 2003; 348: 529–537.

33) Lander, E.S. *et al.* Initial sequencing and analysis of the human genome. *Nature* 2001;409: 860–921

34) Venter, J.C. *et al.* The sequence of the human genome. *Science* 2001;291:1304–1351

35) International HapMap Consortium, The international HapMap project. *Nature* 2003;426: 789–796

36) Redon, R. *et al.* Global variation in copy number in the human genome. *Nature* 2006;4: 444–454

37) Wellcome Trust Case Control Consortium, Genome-wide association study of 14,000 cases of seven common diseases and 3,000 shared controls. *Nature* 2007;447: 661–678

38) 1000 Genomes Project Consortium, A map of human genome variation from population-scale sequencing. *Nature* 2010;467: 1061–1073

39) Hong-Guang Xie & Felix W Frueh Pharmacogenomics step towards personalized medicines future *Medicine* 2005;325-337

40) Pharmacogenomics Today: 21st Century Personalized Medicine Insight Pharma Reports. www.insightpharmareports.com

41) White Papers in Pharmacogenetics ©2013 LUMINEX CORPORATION

42) <http://cpmc1.coriell.org/personalized-medicine>

43) Pirmohamed, M. Warfarin: almost 60 years old and still causing problems. *Br. J. Clin. Pharmacol.* 2006 ;62:509–511

44) Farhad Kamali and Hilary Wynne Pharmacogenetics of Warfarin *Annual Review of Medicine* .2010. Vol. 61: 63-75

- 45) Jonas, D.E. and McLeod, H.L. Genetic and clinical factors relating to warfarin dosing. *Trends Pharmacol. Sci.* 2009 .30, 375–386
- 46) C. Wandel, R. Böcker, H. Böhrer, A. Browne, E. Rügheimer And E. Martin. Midazolam is metabolized by at least three different cytochrome P450 enzymes. *BJA* Volume 73, Issue 5 . 658-661
- 47) <http://www.pedsanesthesia.org/meetings/2008annual/syllabus/Lecture-Galinkin.pdf>
- 48) Ferfusion A, Bevan DR: Mixed neuromuscular block: The effect of precurarization. *Anaesthesia* 1981;36:661-666
- 49) Mehta MP, Sokoll Md, Gergis SD: Accelerated onset of non polarizing neuromuscular blocking drugs: Pancuronium, atracurium, and vecuronium. A comparison with succinylcholine. *Eur J Anaesthesiol* 1980;53:517-520
- 50) Kalow w, Genest K: A method for the detection of atypical forms of human serum cholinesterase: Determination of dibucaine numbers. *Can J Med Sci* 1957;35:339-346
- 51) Ufer M, Mosyagin I, Muhle H, et al. Non-response to antiepileptic pharmacotherapy is associated with the *ABCC2-24C>T* polymorphism in young and adult patients with epilepsy. *Pharmacogenet Genomics*. 2009;19(5):353–362.
- 52). Sisodiya SM, Goldstein DB. Drug resistance in epilepsy: more twists in the tale. *Epilepsia*. 2007;48(12):2369–2370.
- 53) Yogita Ghodke Puranik, Angela K Birnbaum, Susan E Marino, Ghada Ahmed, James C Cloyd, Rory P Rummel, Ilo E Leppik, and Jatinder K Lamba (Jan 2013) Association of carbamazepine major metabolism and transport pathway gene polymorphisms and pharmacokinetics in patients with epilepsy. *Pharmacogenomics*.; 14(1): 35–45. doi: [10.2217/pgs.12.180](https://doi.org/10.2217/pgs.12.180)
- 54) http://www.cuh.org.uk/sites/default/files/publications/PIN1683_carbamazepine.pdf
- 55) <http://www.fda.gov/Drugs/DrugSafety/DrugSafetyNewsletter/UCM148014.pdf>
- 56) Suppiah V, Moldovan M, Ahlenstiel G, Berg T, Weltman M, Abate ML, Bassendine M, Spengler U, Dore GJ, Powell E, Riordan S, Sheridan D, Smedile A, Fragomeli V, Müller T, Bahlo M, Stewart GJ, Booth DR, George J IL28B is associated with response to chronic hepatitis C interferon-alpha and ribavirin therapy. *Nat Genet*. 2009 Oct;41(10):1100-4.
- 57) Afdhal, N.H. et al. Hepatitis C pharmacogenetics: state of the art in 2010. *Hepatology* .2011.53, 336–345
- 58) Jacob Nattermann, Martin Vogel, Hans Dieter Nischalke, Mark Danta, Stefan Mauss, Hans-Joerg Stellbrink, Axel Baumgarten, Christoph Mayr, Raffaele Bruno, Cristina Tural, Gerd Klausen, Bonaventura Clotet, Uwe Naumann, Thomas Lutz, Michael Rausch, Knud Schewe, Bernhard Bienek, Georg Haerter, Tilman Sauerbruch, Juergen K. Rockstroh, 1 and Ulrich Spengler 1. Genetic Variation in IL28B and Treatment-induced Clearance of Hepatitis C Virus in HIV-Positive Patients With Acute and Chronic Hepatitis C. *The Journal of Infectious Diseases* 2011;203:595–601.
- 59) Rauch, A. et al. Genetic variation in IL28B is associated with chronic hepatitis C and treatment failure: a genome-wide association study. *Gastroenterology* .2010.138, 1338–1945 E1–E7

- 60) Sonja Pavlovic, Branka Zukic and Gordana Nikcevic (2012). Pharmacogenomics of Thiopurine SMethyltransferase: Clinical Applicability of Genetic Variants, Clinical Applications of Pharmacogenetics, Dr. Despina Sanoudou (Ed.), ISBN: 978-953-51-0389-9, InTech, Available from: <http://www.intechopen.com/books/clinical-applications-of-pharmacogenetics/pharmacogenomics-of-thiopurines-methyltransferase-clinical-applicability-of-genetic-variants>
- 61) Diane Otterness, Carol Szumlanski, Lynne Lennard, Bjørg Klemetsdal, Jarle Aarbakke, Jeong Ok Park-Hah, Heiko Iven, Kjeld Schmiegelow, Earl Branum, John O'Brien and Richard Weinshilboum. Human thiopurine methyltransferase pharmacogenetics: Gene sequence polymorphisms*Human thiopurine methyltransferase pharmacogenetics: Gene sequence polymorphisms . Clinical Pharmacology & Therapeutics **62**, 60-73 (July 1997) | doi:10.1016/S0009-9236(97)90152-1
- 62) <http://www.epilepsy.com/medications/phenytoin>
- 63) J. Rosemary, A. Surendiran, S. Rajan, C.H. Shashindran & C. Adithan
Influence of the *CYP2C9* & *CYP2C19* polymorphisms on phenytoin hydroxylation in healthy individuals from south India. Indian J Med Res (May 2006)123, 665-670
- 64) Williams DG, Patel A, Howard RF. Pharmacogenetics of codeine metabolism in an urban population of children and its implications for analgesic reliability. Br J Anaesth. 2002;89(6):839-45.
- 65) Williams DG, Patel A, Howard RF: Pharmacogenetics of codeine metabolism in an urban population of children and its implications for analgesic reliability. Br J Anaesth 2002; 89: 839-45
- 66) Madadi P, Ross C, Hayden M, Carleton B, Gaedigk A, Leeder J, Koren G: Pharmacogenetics of Neonatal Opioid Toxicity Following Maternal Use of Codeine During Breastfeeding: A Case-Control Study. Clin Pharmacol Ther 2008
- 67) Aneesh T P, Sonal Sekhar M, Asha Jose, Lekshmi Chandran and Subin Mary Zachariah
Pharmacogenomics: The Right Drug to the Right Person. J Clin Med Res. Oct 2009; 1(4): 191-194
- 68) <http://www.genetics.edu.au/Publications-and-Resources/Genetics-Fact-sheets/FactSheet25>
- 69) Magdum C S, Velingkar V S, Gupta Meenu K. Pharmacogenomics: The search for the Individualized Therapy. Indian Journal of Pharmaceutical Education & Research. 2006;40(2 (April-June)):84-91.
- 70) Lesko LJ, Johnson JA. Academia at the crossroads: education and training in pharmacogenomics. Pers Med. 2012;9:497-506.
- 71) Julie A Johnson. Pharmacogenetics in clinical practice: how far have we come and where are we going? Pharmacogenomics. May 2013; 14(7): 835-843
- 72) Johnson JA, Burkley BM, Langaee TY, Clare-Salzler MJ, Klein TE, Altman RB. Implementing personalized medicine: Development of a cost-effective custom pharmacogenetics genotyping array. Clin Pharmacol Ther. 2012;92(4):437-439
- 73) <https://chemistry.illinoisstate.edu/jfriese/documents/Whatispharmacogenomics.pdf>
- 74) Williams-Jones B, Carriyan OP. Rhetoric and type: where's the ethics in pharmacogenomics? Am J Pharmacogenomics 2003; 3(6): 375-83.

- 75) Lindpainter K., Pharmacogenetics and the future of medical practice. Br J Clin Pharmacol 2002; 54: 221-30.
- 76) Freund CL, Wilfond BS. Emerging ethical issues in pharmacogenomics. Am J Pharmacogenomics 2002; 2(4): 273-81
- 77) Roses AD. Pharmacogenetics and future drug development and delivery. Lancet 2000; 355: 1358-61.
- 78) Bansal V, Kumar V and Medhi B., Future Challenges of Pharmacogenomics in Clinical Practice, JK Science, 2005; 7 (3): 176-179.
- 79) Meghani N M. Tailor Made Medicinal Approach: Pharmacogenomics. International Journal Of Pharma And Bio Sciences 2011; 2(1).
- 80) Singh D. Ethical issues of Pharmacogenetics must be addressed, say Nuffield Council. BMJ 2003; 327: 701.